

Integrating Ethnic Interests In Nigeria For Unity Through The Media

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Abstract

The media in every society are part of the government but not of the government. This is why the media are seen and regarded as the fourth arm of government after the executive, the legislature and the judiciary. The media are of the government because no government universally, can function effectively devoid of the media. On the other hand, the media are not of the government because they function to guide and guard the government from itself and therefore cannot be part of it. It takes the unbiased, objective observer to appreciate the intricacies of governance and that is what makes the media a force to reckon with: their relative objectivity; relative because man is by nature not impeccable. Nigeria is a multi-ethnic society in dire need of unity, of integration and of cohesion. This is a task that needs the most logical, intellectual, rational and objective minds to tackle. These minds reside among media workers and practitioners who can take the challenge of re-orienting these ethnic interests on the need for unity and peaceful co-existence. This paper is channelled towards addressing how the media can help Nigeria in the task of achieving national integration and unity. Before this can be done however, the media must be free from all forms of control. It uses the literary research method to interrogate the ways the media can achieve this. It concludes that the issues of national cohesion, unity and peaceful coexistence are a matter of choice and the media can help the differing ethnic interests to make this choice.

Keywords: Media, Ethnicity, Re-orientation, Government, Unity

Introduction

The media are part of us. Indeed, the media constitute a larger part of our existence and daily life. That is perhaps, why everybody has an idea of what the media are, even if such knowledge is not accurate or comprehensive. The media are generally categorized into two broad types: Print and Electronic. However, as carriers of

communication experience, the media are also agents of change and this change they bring about through communication. Communication on its part comprises verbal and non-verbal types. But our focus in this paper is concerned with the electronic means of communication, that is, the electronic media, notably, television, radio, film and the social media, all of which we

suffuse as media in this paper. The umbrella usage is necessary because of the similarity in their functions and use. We recognise and acknowledge the fact that film, also called movie or motion picture is not a conventional news medium, but it certainly does purvey issues of general concern as well as have the capacity to influence humanity even more than the conventional news media. And since our concern is not news per se, the movie becomes germane to our discussion.

Again, the reason for this umbrella grouping may seem obvious or not, but to make it clearer, the effects of the media are not easily attributable to only one medium. All the media pool together to make impact on the audience, some may be more pronounced in their effect while some may not be so obvious. All the media however, contribute to whatever effects that are attributed to them and since these effects are gradual and prone to time, the best bet is to lump them together. And, as Lawrence Grossberg (2006) and his colleagues have noted, “the media have become so intertwined with every aspect of our reality that the line between the two, media and reality, has become blurred and even porous,” (7). Not only that, our lives as presently constituted would appear to be meaningless devoid of the media. With the evolution of internet and the incursion of social media in the present century, the daily routines of the average human being, elite or

not, appears incomplete without contact with any form of media. Indeed, some people feel incomplete if on a given day they do not hear their phone ring, a chat, text message, Yahoo messenger tone, etc. or in fact, any sign that someone somewhere has thought of them!

Conceptual Clarifications

When in 1964, Herbert Marshall McLuhan published his seminal book entitled: *The Media: the Extensions of Man* and made several speculations, many people misunderstood him while some thought him mad. But today, the media are not only the extensions of man; they have become the entire man. Indeed, man as an entity can no longer be contemplated outside the media. The media have become so much a part of man that without them man would be totally lost. Technology has seen to that. The digitization and globalisation of communication have made it extremely difficult if not out-rightly impossible for man to function effectively without the media. As Peter Babatunde Adedara and John Ayotunde Isola Bewaji make us understand, “the mass media are the diversified collection of media tools or technologies that facilitate the spread of information and entertainment to a vast number of customers,” (1). Again, Grossberg and his associates submit that, “the media have the power to engage and entertain, to create and destroy, to open spaces and to close them,” (28). They see media from their ability

to do and undo, as it were. The media, as man, can be seen from several perspectives because like man, they are complex and can therefore not be compartmentalized in one definition. Campbell, Martin and Fabos in the 2009 updated edition of their book, *Media & Culture: an introduction to mass communication*, have this to say about the media.

Although often labelled and discussed disparagingly as “the media,” mass communication institutions are not a single entity. The mass media constitute a wide variety of industries and merchandise, from documentary news programs about famines in Africa to infomercials about vegetable slices or psychic therapists. The word *media* is, after all, a Latin plural form for the singular noun *medium*. Television, newspapers, music, movies, magazines, books, billboards, radio, broadcast satellites, and the Internet are all part of the media; and they each remain quite capable of either producing worthy products or pandering to society’s worst desires, prejudices, and stereotypes (10).

Although they observe that it is not so good to lump the entire media institutions under one umbrella, they also acknowledge that such is what generally obtains and that it leads to some form of distrust of the media. But whether the media are to be trusted or not is not before us. Our focus here is to examine how they can be deployed in their collective to

help bring unity and cohesion to an otherwise multi-ethnic society such as Nigeria. This means that we must necessarily lump them together that is, the electronic and print though our argument may tilt more towards the electronic media. The power which the media wield is indicative of the fact that when deliberately and conscientiously directed, the media can be used to achieve just about whatever objective the user wants to achieve. Adelakun seems to echo the above submission when he cites Odunlami who says:

The media in Nigeria from time immemorial is (*sic*) reputed to be very vibrant and this could be understood from the process of its (*sic*) evolution. If the Nigeria (n) press for instance is rated as the freest in Africa, or better put, one of the freest in the world, such freedom is earned by dint of its consistency, resilience and dynamism, and not through any goodwill it enjoys (*sic*) from successive governments in the country (64-65).

The above citation though referring to the media in general, was actually, directed at the Nigerian press. Thus, if the press, which by the way, was said to be quite instrumental to the attainment of Nigeria’s independence, can do so much, the likelihood is there that with the active support of movies from Nollywood, there is no doubt that much more can be achieved. Before going further to interrogate how this can be done, let us look at some other constituents of this topic: Ethnic interest,

integration and unity. We will start by looking at the words, 'ethnicity', 'ethnicism' before considering 'ethnic interest'. So, what does 'ethnicity' mean and how can it be rated against the word, 'nationality'? Naturally, ethnicity would be that which arises from ethnic, which itself is related to tribe, as in one's traditional or ancestral place of origin as opposed to one's nation or country. It generally identifies one with his/her tribal affiliation/interest in preference to the national outlook. And it is pretty common in a multi-ethnic state where the members see themselves first, as belonging to their ethnic/tribal affiliation as against their national interest which they see more as a political appendage than a natural outflow of their origin. As Afamefuna Mordi makes us to understand in his inaugural lecture which he titled, *Ethnicism: Our yesterday in our today*, delivered on the 29th of November, 2005:

I am definitely the first Nigerian Sociologist to articulate the concept and the use of ethnicism which I have in my several researches and work defined as the practice that emerges out of ethnicity in which the interest of the dominant ethnic group or groups is presented as if it is the interest of everybody occupying the geopolitical entity. While the ones before me have written on ethnicity and the plural nature of Nigerian Society, Nnoli (1978), Otite (1990), they have neglected to discuss the meaning and the practice men make out of

ethnicity which I have in my researches and works of over two decades referred to as Ethnicism. Further, unlike the Sociologists before me who were either Functionalists or Marxists in their approach, I have in my own modest way posited the discourse of ethnicism on a holistic pedestrian thus marshalling out the point that it is an ideology, a world view, a belief system, and a practice that emerges out of ethnicity (which I have referred to as ethnicism) (55-56).

Mordi goes on to argue that "ethnicism as an ideology should be seen as a practice in which dominant ethnic group or groups in alliance camouflage their interest as if it is the interest of everybody in the Geopolitical entity," (56). We have taken pains to draw elaborately from the citation because the author took his time to make us understand that ethnicity and ethnicism, at least from his point of view are one and the same thing. Again, being the first to use the word, 'ethnicism' and making us to know that he prefers it to 'ethnicity' we can only assume that they mean the same thing. Whether ethnicity or ethnicism, the fact remains that both are concerned with placing ethnic interests above national concerns. This is the focus of this paper: how to reverse the trend of ethnic interests coming or taking second position in the lives of the citizens of Nigeria, using the media.

We will now briefly look at the word, "integration." Simply put, to integrate means,

to bring together, to join, to incorporate and unite objects, things or people that have somehow been separated or dispersed, or scattered from one another. Integration is therefore the act of integrating, of bringing together as one things or people that were either part of the main before or are independent of one another. In the case of Nigeria, to integrate can be said to be synonymous with amalgamation. The various nations that make up Nigeria were amalgamated in the year 1914 by Lord Fredrick Laggard, representing the British colonial government. One would have thought that since the amalgamation took place, the idea of integration is no longer necessary. This line of thought would be erroneous, however, because the ethnic nationalities which were then amalgamated over a century ago are still not comfortable with the amalgamation hence the subject of integrating or more appropriately, re-integrating them becomes germane. This is not a mean task. Indeed, the present constitution of Nigeria and the agitations for restructuring makes the task of re-integration rather complex and beyond any single individual or even government. This is why the media are selected to engage the challenges of educating, enlightening, informing and re-orienting these ethnic interests on the need and importance of accepting to live together as one nation, notwithstanding their unique differences in

religion, politics, culture, land mass, world view, philosophy, and many others.

The argument in favour of the media as suitable for this task has been proven because of all the institutions and corporate bodies that are not directly involved in governance, “the press (the media) is free because the public as a whole want it to be free. This inevitably means that the public is concerned in the way its freedom is exercised,” (12). This freedom of the media must be recognized by all and be embedded in the constitution for it to be acceptable. It is particularly important for the media to be free because most times those who make the laws are often the owners of the media and they are more often than not those who break the law and try to control the media. Public/Society’s interest in the media is predicated on the fact that the media serve as voice of the voiceless, are not beholden to anybody, government or institution and in civilised societies even media owners do not dictate to them; not the way they do in developing countries anyway. Thus, the media are relatively free to operate and the public equally has a certain measure of confidence in the media unlike other government agencies. Again, the Nigerian media have antecedents in their role during the colonial era especially in the achievement of the nation’s independence. All these are in their favour to tackle the contentious issue of integrating the different ethnic nations which make up Nigeria into one

holistic and united country. The issue of Nigeria's unity is such that no single individual, tribe or even government can actualise it. It requires a concerted effort of every stakeholder to realise and the media have the responsibility to coordinate this task. In this case, the media would be excused to work on the side of government as they indeed ought to work always and at all times on the side of justice, fairness and uphold what is right.

How can the media achieve this feat?

The media whether electronic or print have the power of choice. In other words, they have the selective power and authority of preference to choose their diction, select the right images and also have the power of control. This is particularly true of the feature film where the director exercises control over all the stages of production. This control enables the director to have an array of choices- of man, material and technology to be deployed to put his message across based on his objective. Now, the objective of the media/filmmaker in this case is the integration of the ethnic nationalities and nations which constitute Nigeria. The media can do this in any of the following ways:

- **Selectivity:** This is perhaps the most cherished factor in the arsenal of the media practitioner be it the print or the electronic media. The ability to choose his diction,

select his images, decide his camera angles, choose his caption and its size, pick the actors/actresses he wants, determine his story slant, point of view, what to emphasize or ignore, among many other factors at his disposal, give him the control he needs to tell his story and report his news as he deems fit.

- **Visuals:** Again, whether your story is for the screen or for the print media, provided it is not for radio, visuals are of utmost importance. Inasmuch as font size and spacing are important in the print medium, photographs are of more significance whenever and wherever they occur. The photographic image, though still, has a force and a power that is difficult to ignore. As Greg Lewis has observed, "visual language is often more powerful than verbal language," (6). Indeed, visual language unlike verbal language has something for everybody. Even the illiterate can watch the printed words on paper and admire their arrangement much like the photograph. As Carpenter has also observed, "it has been said that words make us think and pictures make us feel," (92). The visual image is indeed, an image that has a message for all even if the message conveys different meaning to the viewers.
- **The Camera:** The visual language acquires motion with the aid of the camera. This is an added advantage for

the filmmaker. He can tell the story of Nigeria by tracing the origin, immediate and remote causes of disaffection and disunity in the country and counter it with images of peaceful and harmonious co-existence. The filmmaker can bring peace to a troubled land by emphasising only the areas where peace prevails; creating an atmosphere of healthy living, by showing where for instance, an Hausa family, can harbour an Igbo family, in the case of ethnic uprising in the north and the reverse, if in the east. Such images carry empathy and are not far-fetched as they have been known to occur in reality. The filmmaker knows how to deploy the inherent attributes of the camera such as lenses, movement, angles, etc. all combined with his creative ingenuity to achieve his objective.

- Language: Whether verbal, visual or non-verbal, choosing the language of communication is essential for the communicator to achieve utmost success. For the filmmaker, his choice of diction for his dialogue is without doubt necessary for him to succeed. As Ewhrudjakpor, Ijeh and Ighovie, have noted, “the mass media is (sic) key to fostering unity in a society with diversities like Nigeria. This is because mass communication proves to be very effective in orientating and mobilising the people to pursue common goals,” (64). One sure way to actualise this

is through a careful selection of the language of communication whether for the print or the electronic media. Recognising that language is at the nexus of much of if not nearly all humanities troubles, it becomes vital to know how to use language in all its forms-verbal, non-verbal, visual, literal, figurative, civil, or uncivil to achieve a set purpose.

- Composition: “Composition- the arrangement of characters and objects within the screen **frame**, - is, first of all, about that frame, which is constituted by the borders that contain the image,” (Kolker, 52). For the filmmaker, composition is an important element in the art of story-telling. It consists of all the elements with which a story is told, from camera movement to camera angles; from modes of transitions to selection of theme music, and indeed every other thing that goes into the film frame, including the actor’s costumes and props. And it goes on like that frame by frame until the story is finished. It is a unique element in the hands of the filmmaker.
- Editing: “The foundation of film art is editing,” (Lindgren, 54). Experts have also called editing “the art that conceals art.” Editing is, perhaps, the greatest element in filmmaking. It is indeed the film itself. As Lindgren has noted while citing John Grierson, one of the greatest filmmakers of

all times, “You photograph the natural life, but you also, by your juxtaposition of detail, create an interpretation of it,” (73). Thus, editing is the real story because without editing, no film would be worth the pleasure or the message. It is through editing that the filmmaker brings out the best there is in his message. He does not need to preoccupy himself with copying reality, but he must of necessity provide an interpretation of it. And this is because the movie is not only a cultural force it is also propagandist in nature. This is why it is most suitable as an agent for the mobilisation of the ethnic nations in Nigeria towards a unified whole. As Lindgren again says while citing Anderson:

The importance of the cinema as a cultural and propagandist force is a matter of fact also. Everyone who has seen more than half-a-dozen films with his eyes open knows that if the cinema does not create the significant social movements of our time, it intimately reflects them. And that it provides a reflection just as intimate- and just as significant- of social stagnation. (177).

From the foregoing, one can see that the motion picture is not only suited to create the enabling environment for the integration of the ethnic nationalities in Nigeria, it can also, alongside the other media of mass communication, actually bring it about. This,

they can do, by consciously and deliberating bombarding the populace with messages and stories whose thematic preoccupations are those of oneness, togetherness, peace, unity, peaceful and harmonious co-existence as noted above. It must be noted that the points mentioned above are not exhaustive in any way. To further buttress the point already made that the media can indeed bring about unity to the different, ethnic, religious and political interests in Nigeria, here is a paragraph length quotation from Doris Graber’s *Mass Media and American Politics*:

The media often serve as attitude and behaviour models. In the process of image creation, the media indicate which views and behaviours are acceptable and even praiseworthy in a given society and which are unacceptable or outside the mainstream. Audiences can learn how to conduct themselves in ordinary social and work situations, how to cope with personal crises, and how to evaluate major social institutions like the medical profession or the police. Media stories also indicate what is deemed important or unimportant by America’s dominant groups, what conforms to prevailing standards of justice and morality, and how various events are related to each other. In the process the media present a set of cultural values that their audiences are likely to accept in whole or in part as typical of American

society. The media thus help to integrate and homogenize American society. (3).

Inasmuch as the media have been said to have such powers of achieving cohesion, unity and oneness; the people to be so united must first recognise and accept that such objective is desirable. And this is where the Nigerian situation becomes germane. The ordinary citizens of Nigeria, irrespective of their geographical location, cultural dissimilarities, religious and or, socio-political differences are highly malleable and thus can be easily united and integrated. The problem however, is the political elites from the various ethnic and tribal nations, especially the three major ones- Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa-, who, perhaps, on account of their own selfish interests, refuse to sow seeds of unity in the country right from the moment when they were amalgamated to constitute one Nigeria in 1914!

Writing on the necessity for using film to present the African/Nigerian world-view, Obi cites Ayakoroma as follows:

The ability to create our own images and capture our own stories has given us a voice and a power to change perceptions of ourselves, our surrounding, and our cultures, both locally and internationally, which is what Imasuen succeeded in doing with the film by projecting Nigerian image in the global arena. Such projection of culture has increased research efforts in Nollywood films by

scholars to decipher how best to package, market and transmit the by-product of film and video works because every country today is looking within the precincts of its cultural milieu to explore and device useful platforms to enable it employ covertly, the instruments of culture via the arts, to market its national agenda to its people and the rest of the world. (Obi, 224-225).

Obi further says, “with this, Nollywood becomes the avenue to launder Nigeria’s battered image through the films that could arouse the interest of viewers positively through transmitting of culture against such negative situations in Nigeria such as political instability occasioned by bad leadership,” (225). By its nature and given its inherent qualities of the director having control over all the stages of production, the motion picture should be at the forefront of the vanguard for the integration of ethnic interests in Nigeria. The other media like television, print, billboards, advertising, internet, even live stage should provide support services to the movie in this regard.

As noted earlier, the problem with Nigeria’s unity and cohesion of the various ethnic nationalities is the leadership which continuously engage in discriminatory tendencies in their behaviours, utterances, even policies which always pitch the people against each other and the tribes against one another. They use the people as politicians use

journalists in their climb up the political ladder. As Conrad Fink makes us understand:

Today, we repeatedly see public officials support- and court- a free press during their climb to power. All are aware of course, that favourable image in newspapers and on television is a prerequisite to political success. Yet once office is attained, some political figures tire of media scrutiny. Then often comes withdrawal from frequent contact with reporters (denial of access, a very real form of censorship) and erection of barriers to the free flow of information. Sometimes there is outright distortion or lying, (35-6).

There is no doubt that the above scenario is a prevalent issue in the Nigerian situation especially in the present regime of Muhammed Buhari, Nigeria's retired army General, now President, where, for example, the information minister, Lai Mohammed, has been known to have multiple tongues, thereby creating credibility problem to the regime. As Godfrey Enita has observed with reference to the causes of conflict in Nigeria, "this perhaps, accounts for the very high level of ethnic, religious and political conflicts in Nigeria, with an equally alarming proportion of casualty rate, resulting from the conflicts. Conflicts in various forms of manifestation continue to thrive in Nigeria due to bad and insensitive leadership, driven by corruption, greed, quest for power, forceful acquisition of primitive wealth and mediocrity," (52). Thus,

leadership of the country must realise the importance of the task ahead.

Expectedly, for the media to succeed in this noble task, they must necessarily make use of propaganda which is a very effective and successful weapon in the hands of any good government provided it is deployed for the benefit of the people; otherwise, it is an instrument for deliberate and conscious misrule and misinformation in the hands of any government that is channelled towards deceit and autocracy. As Noam Chomsky would have us believe, "State propaganda, when supported by the educated classes and when no deviation is permitted from it, can have a big effect. It was a lesson learned by Hitler and many others, and it has been pursued to this day," (13). Propaganda, when supported by the authoritative force of government, with the active involvement of the media, can have an unparallel success. Ordinarily, governments globally make use of propaganda in one form or another and it is indeed, a good instrument of governance. In the case of Nigeria's unity, without the leaders pandering to and beating the drums of disunity, propaganda can be very effective in the bid to achieving a united Nigeria. In fact, nothing should be left to chance in bringing about the integration of the ethnic nations which make up Nigeria into a unified entity. If only the leaders and the ethnic pundits really want a united Nigeria, the media can help to

bring this much needed oneness about. Nigeria is not the only multi-ethnic nation in the world. We have the United States of America (USA) as a good example in this regard. We need to get rid of such weak practices as the recognition of state of origin instead of state of residence; quota system, zoning and allocations, appointments, etc on the basis of tribe. Agreed, if merit is allowed to prevail as it really ought to, it would engender healthy competition as the disadvantaged state or tribe would buckle up in order to meet the challenge. However, if it is well handled, the issue of tribe would have given way to the projection of state of residence. Indeed, what gives ethnic and tribal sentiments room to operate is the denial of certain rights to people who are purportedly not from a particular tribe even when they have lived there all their lives and may have lost track with their supposed state of origin or home state.

Chomsky in an excerpt of what appears like the introduction which he captured on the cover of his book, already cited, says: “the role of the media in contemporary politics forces us to ask: what kind of a world and what kind of a society we want to live in, and in particular, in what sense of democracy do we want this to be a democratic society?” (9). These salient questions certainly beg answers. The type of democracy we want, or have, has direct bearing on the type of people we are or want to be. This is where the media

come in. The media have what it takes to help us be the people we want to be, for good or for ill. Media historians and scholars always remind us of the role the press played in the attainment of Nigeria’s independence. It is not therefore beyond the full complement of the media with the added support of the motion picture and the internet, with its paraphernalia of social media, to actualise the quest for tribal, and or ethnic integration of the many and diverse tribes which presently constitute the Nigerian nation. All it requires is a positive mindset and sincere commitment on the part of the country’s leadership. This is because such laudable task would amount to nought and even when global media get involved, it would still amount to a wasted effort if the leadership of the country pays lip service to it or sabotage the effort by their insincerity and selfish ethnic and tribal dichotomy. It therefore goes without saying that unity like peace is a choice that must be made. However, the decision is in the hands of policy and decision makers to make. On them and them alone lies the fate of Nigeria even as they have mauled and reduced it to such a ridiculous laughing stock in the comity of nations to the point that the country which was once the pride of Black Africa is now synonymous with corruption and all manners of negative tendencies.

The media are there to create awareness, sensitize the people, inform them, guide and

direct the people; mobilize, orientate and re-orientate them, educate by illustration and by condemning what is wrong. Indeed, media content, whether it is in print, electronic, non-verbal, visual, audio, whatever, must be directed aggressively towards this one course. All that is required is the agreement by the stakeholders, especially the government in power, to adopt a policy designed to actualize the objective of living together. The country's diversity is not an excuse; indeed, it is the diverse and multi-ethnic nature of the country that gives the impetus for the propagation of the theory of integration! There would be no necessity and in fact, no basis for discussing integration in a mono-ethnic society. We are desirous of integration and unity because we are different, diverse and multi-ethnic. It is for this reason that we need the media and communication at all levels, intra personal, inter personal, small group and mass, to help us in this task. The diversity of the country makes the choice of different media to bring the multi-ethnic people together using their different languages.

Conclusion

Unity, peace, oneness or their opposites-division, war/crisis, and disunity, are all dependent variables which depend on the choices we make. In the case of Nigeria and as it affects national integration of the ethnic nations into one unified, coherent whole or entity, were it left to me, I would think that the

subject should not be compromised. Nigeria is certainly not the only country that is multi-ethnic, we have America, South Africa, Kenya, China, among others, maybe not multi-ethnic in the same degree, but multi-ethnic nonetheless. Therefore, it is the decision of the people through their leaders to choose to be one or not. They have for good or bad lived together for over a century, at least, from 1914-2018; it was at a time when most of the world was arguably crude, uncivilized in comparison with what obtains today, yet, the ethnic nationalities managed to live in unity how much now they have an array of media of all types to help in expediting the process. But this cannot be achieved if the media are in the control and selfish grip of those who are agents and proponents of ethnic or tribal interest against the national objective.

The clamour for restructuring the country which has recently gained prominence in the wake of the insecurity, religious intolerance, terrorism of the most unbearable nature, political instability, corruption extravaganza, etc. can become meaningful only if the integration of the diverse ethnic and tribal entities is made a condition for such integration. Also, the elimination of such absurd policies as quota system, state of origin, zoning at all levels should be jettisoned so that merit, justice and fairness are enthroned as a necessity. These the media can help us actualise provided we are determined

to use them to such end. Nothing is impossible for the willing heart and as the saying goes impossibility only exists in the dictionary of a fool. Again, since impossibility does not exist in the motion picture industry, making Nigeria one nation does not really pose a challenge for the media once they are given the task. But first, Nigerians in general and their leaders in particular, must accept that unity of the multi-ethnic nationalities and their integration into one strong united country is not only necessary and desirable, but it is also a condition for broaching the subject of restructuring.

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